

Formulation And Evaluation of Ibuprofen Loaded Microsponges for Topical Drug Delivery System

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ABSTRACT

Microsponges are highly porous, polymeric microspheres developed to enhance localized and controlled delivery of therapeutic agents to the skin. The present study was aimed at the formulation and evaluation of ibuprofen-loaded microsponges to achieve controlled drug release and reduce dose-related side effects. Microsponges were prepared by the quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion method using suitable polymers. Ibuprofen was selected as a model anti-inflammatory drug due to its short biological half-life and frequent dosing requirements. The prepared microsponges were evaluated for Physical appearance, particle size, surface morphology using Optical microscopy, drug loading efficiency, entrapment efficiency, and production yield, pH. Scanning electron microscopy revealed that the microsponges were spherical in shape with a porous surface structure. The results indicate that microsphere-based drug delivery systems can effectively enhance drug stability, sustained release, provide controlled release, and improve therapeutic performance, making them a promising approach for topical drug delivery of ibuprofen.

Keywords: Novel drug delivery system, Microsponges, Eudragit L 100, Ibuprofen, Quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion method.

INTRODUCTION

Ibuprofen is one of the most widely used NSAIDs (non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs) in the class of drugs derived from propionic acid. Because of its potent analgesic, antipyretic, and anti-inflammatory qualities, it is commonly administered for conditions such as muscle discomfort, arthritis, dysmenorrhea, fever, and soft-tissue injuries. Despite its proven therapeutic benefits, the conventional administration of ibuprofen, whether oral or topical, typically has disadvantages such as gastrointestinal irritation, a short biological half-life, and changes in plasma drug levels. These drawbacks highlight the need for improved drug delivery strategies that can optimize therapeutic efficacy while lowering side effects. Ibuprofen-loaded microsponges help prolong drug release by controlling the drug's diffusion from the polymeric matrix. Because of its mild lipophilicity, ibuprofen is efficiently contained within the microsponges, and its release may be tailored by selecting the appropriate polymers, solvents, and

processing conditions. This regulated release reduces the frequency of doses and improves overall therapeutic outcomes by preserving constant drug concentrations at the application site. Additionally, microsphere-based formulations improve the visual and sensory aspects of topical treatments by eliminating greasiness and improving spreadability. Reducing systemic absorption and associated side effects is a significant benefit of utilizing microsponges for ibuprofen administration. The initial burst release of conventional topical gels or ointments frequently results in irritation or inadequate long-term activity. By offering a gradual, steady, and consistent release profile, microsponges reduce this issue. By shielding the active ingredient from light, oxidation, and degradation, they can help improve drug stability. Microsponges are an adaptable ibuprofen carrier in formulations like gels, creams, or lotions due to their high loading capacity. All things considered, adding ibuprofen to microsphere-based

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delivery systems presents a viable method for enhancing the medication's therapeutic efficacy.

By offering prolonged release, increased stability, less discomfort, and better patient convenience, it overcomes the drawbacks of conventional ibuprofen formulations. Ibuprofen-loaded microsponges are therefore attracting a lot of attention in pharmaceutical research and development, especially for topical therapy of inflammatory and painful disorders. The present need for safer, more efficient, and patient-friendly medication administration systems is met by this creative strategy. Drug delivery is the process of giving a medication to humans or animals in order to achieve a therapeutic result. For many years, pharmaceutical dosage forms such as tablets, pills, capsules, ointments, creams, liquids, injectables, suppositories, and gels—which are regarded as standard dosage forms—have been used to treat both acute and chronic illnesses. traditional dosing forms. Traditional transdermal applications of gels release the medication as soon as they are

applied, which causes the medication to build up and irritate skin layers. The active ingredient can be spread out in a liquid or applied straight to the skin in a nearly pure form.

Recently new approaches in the novel drug delivery systems introduced are:

- ❖ Oral Drug Delivery System (DDS)
- ❖ Mucosal DDS
- ❖ Nasal DDS
- ❖ Parenteral DDS
- ❖ Vaginal DDS
- ❖ Intrauterine DDS
- ❖ Ocular DDS
- ❖ Transdermal DDS

Table No.1 Carrier System for Drug Delivery

Carrier System	TYPES	
	Vesicular system	Microparticulate system
Colloidal carrier	Liposome	Nanocapsules
	Niosome	Nanoparticles
	Immunoliposomes	Microsponges

MICROSPONGE: AN APPROACH FOR TOPICAL DELIVERY

Microsponges are a new, regulated medicinal product with a wide range of uses. They have the capacity to encapsulate a variety of medications, both liquid and solid. compliance. Overall, microsponges offer a promising approach in pharmaceutical formulations, enhancing drug delivery outcomes and patient satisfaction. By taking advantage of the special structure and physiology of human skin, microsponges offer a significant advantage in the administration of dermatological medicines. They provide increased effectiveness when applied to human skin. They minimize local side effects while providing increased efficacy. is essential to their topical Microsponges' remarkable entrapment effectiveness, which enables them to absorb more

than six times their own weight, is one of their main advantages. Even at high temperatures and over a wide pH range of 1 to 11, these microsponges show remarkable stability. compatibility when added to liquid or semi-solid dosages and suspended in different carriers forms by giving the medication a regulated release. Microsponges add to the product's elegance by assuring stability and non-irritating medication release. qualities that enhance patient applicability.

DEFINITION:

The tiny sponge-like particles that make up microsponges are porous, polymeric, microscopic drug delivery systems that have the ability to trap active medicinal components within their network. They are usually between 5 and 300 µm in diameter

and have many interconnected pores that enable targeted, regulated, and prolonged drug release. By releasing the medication gradually at the site of action, microsponges increase the stability of

medications, lessen discomfort, and boost efficacy. These qualities make them popular in topical, oral, and cosmetic formulations to increase patient compliance and therapeutic efficacy.

Fig no.1 Structure of Microsponges

Higher concentrations of active substances are needed to produce therapeutic effects because many conventional drug delivery methods are ineffective at delivering medications. Because of these restrictions, sophisticated drug delivery methods are being investigated more and more to accomplish site-specific and regulated drug release. A Polymer-based microspheres with a substantially cross-linked structure are known as microsphere systems. They can encapsulate a wide range of active pharmacological substances since they are sufficiently flexible. These qualities make microsponges popular for applications involving controlled and extended drug administration. Microsponges are designed to effectively administer

a pharmaceutically active drug at the lowest feasible dose, minimize adverse effects, and enhance stability, elegance, and flexibility in formulation. The drug release profile can also be changed with these. The microsphere system can stop an excess of a component from building up in the dermis and epidermis. These goods are often packaged in conventional ways and contain a very high concentration of active substances. Microsponges come in conventional forms like lotions, gels, or creams and have a fairly high concentration of active chemicals. A variety of active substances, including anti-infective, anti-fungal, and anti-inflammatory drugs, can be transported via microsponges, which are polymeric delivery systems made of porous microspheres.

Table No.2 List of marketed products

Sr.no	Active agent	Application
1	Sunscreens	Long-lasting product efficacy, with improved protection against sunburns and sun-related injuries, even at elevated concentration and with reduced irritancy and sensitization
2.	Anti-acne, e.g., Benzoyl peroxide	Maintained efficacy with decreased skin irritation and sensitization
3.	Anti-inflammatory e.g. hydrocortisone	Long lasting activity with reduction of skin allergic response and dermatoses
4.	Anti-dandruffs, e.g., zinc pyrithione	Reduced unpleasant odour with lowered irritation and extended safety and efficacy.

❖ **Advantages**

- 1) Avoidance of First Pass Metabolism.
- 2) Suitability for self-medication.
- 3) Microsponges remain stable at pH 1-11 and 130°C.
- 4) Microsponges are suitable with most vehicles and substances.
- 5) Enhances thermal, chemical, and physical stability.
- 6) Avoidance of absorption challenges.
- 7) Easy termination of medication if necessary.
- 8) Avoidance of gastrointestinal incompatibility.
- 9) Microsponges are biosafe and allow programmable release.
- 10) Enables immiscible product incorporation.

❖ **Disadvantages**

- 1) Skin irritation or dermatitis may occur due to the drug or excipient and this can lead to discomfort and adverse reactions.
- 2) Low drug loading capacity.
- 3) Use of organic solvents may cause toxicity.
- 4) Complex and time-consuming preparation.
- 5) Risk of initial burst release.
- 6) Scale-up process is challenging.
- 7) Moisture-sensitive system.
- 8) Poor stability in presence of light and high temperature.
- 9) Cannot incorporate water soluble drugs.

Objectives

1. To formulate Ibuprofen-loaded microsponges using suitable polymer(s) and preparation technique.
2. To optimize formulation parameters such as drug-polymer ratio, solvent system, and stirring conditions
3. To evaluate the prepared microsponges for particle size, morphology, production yield, entrapment efficiency, and drug loading.
4. To incorporate optimized microsponges into a suitable topical gel base.
5. To assess the potential of Ibuprofen microsponges for sustained drug release and improved topical delivery.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Material: Ibuprofen, Eudragit RS 100, Ethyl cellulose, PVA, Dichloromethane, Methanol, glycerol.

Methods:

Ibuprofen microsponges were prepared by quasi emulsion solvent diffusion method by using different drug.

Quasi-Emulsion Solvent Diffusion Method:

The microsponges containing the anti-inflammatory and Antipyretic drug Ibuprofen, as the core material was prepared by Quasi emulsion Method according to the formula given in table no. 3 the process involved formation of quasi-emulsion of two different phases i.e. internal phase and external phase similar to the emulsion.

- 1) The drug-polymer solution's internal phase prepared in 10 milliliters of dichloromethane, a volatile solvent.
- 2) After that, it was vigorously stirred into the external phase, which included the aqueous 1% (1g/100 ml water) polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) solution.

- 3) A sufficient amount of glycerol (1-2 ml) was injected to promote plasticity. Discrete emulsion globules known as quasi emulsion globules are created as a result of stirring.
- 4) The stirring was continued up to 3 hrs till the insoluble, rigid microparticles i.e. microsponges is formed.
- 5) Then it was filtered to separate the microsponges and dried it oven for 3hrs .

Fig no. 2. Process of stirring

Formula for Microsponges formulation

Table no. 3

Sr No.	Ingredient	F1	F2
1.	Ibuprofen	1gm	1gm
2.	Ethyl cellulose	1gm	2gm
3.	Polyvinyl Alcohol	0.5gm	1gm
4.	Dichloromethane	10ml	10ml
5.	Glycerol	1ml	1ml
6.	Water	100ml	100ml

EVALUATION PARAMETER OF IBUPROFEN MICROSPONGES:

1. Physical Appearance:

The formulation's physical characteristics, including color, consistency, and the existence of any obvious irregularities, were evaluated visually.

2. Percentage yield:

It is necessary to gather and weigh the microsponges produced from different formulations. In this case, the total weight of the medication and polymer utilized in the production procedure will be divided by the actual weight of the microsponges. This computation makes it possible to evaluate the proportion of medication contained in the microsponges, offering information on the formulation's effectiveness. The yield percentage was computed using the formula that follows:

$$\% \text{ Yield} = \frac{\text{Practical yield of microsponges}}{\text{Total weight of drug and polymer}} \times 100$$

3. Drug content:

Each batch of microsponges containing 100 mg of ibuprofen should be accurately weighed and crushed. After that, the powder should be put in a 100 ml volumetric flask and adjusted with pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. To bring the solution up to par, phosphate buffer should be added after it has been filtered. Whatmann filter paper No. 44 was then used to filter the mixture. A precise amount of the solution (1 ml) should be taken after filtering and diluted up to 10 ml with pH 7.4. Following filtering, a precise amount of the solution (1 ml) should be obtained and diluted with pH 7.4 phosphate buffer up to 10 ml. A precise volume (1 ml) should be pipetted out of this diluted solution, and pH 7.4 phosphate buffer should be used to further dilute it up to 10 ml. A spectrophotometer should be used to measure the final solution's absorbance at 264 nm.

$$\% \text{ Drug Content} = \frac{\text{Actual drug content of microsponges}}{\text{Total amount of microsponges}} \times 100$$

4. Optical microscopy:

Microsponges' surface appearance and form are examined using microscopy. A tiny sample is put on a glass slide and examined under a microscope.

5. Entrapment efficiency (EE)/ Loading efficiency:

Actual Drug Content: 100 mg of precisely weighed microsponges were used. They were ground into a powder and extracted using a 100 ml technique. Additionally, it was serially diluted using phosphate buffer 7.8 at pH 7.4. Ibuprofen drug concentration was determined by measuring absorbance in a UV spectrophotometer at 260 nm using pH 7.4 phosphate buffer as a blank. The investigations were conducted in duplicate. The entrapment effectiveness and real drug content were purposefully chosen as:

- Actual drug content (%)
= $(M_{act}/M_{ms}) \times 100$
- Entrapment efficiency (%)
= $M_{act}/M_{the} \times 100$

where M_{the} is the theoretical amount of ibuprofen in microsponges, M_{ms} is the weighed quantity of microsponges, and M_{act} is the actual amount of ibuprofen in microsponges.

6. pH:

A digital pH meter was used to determine the formulation's pH. The formulation's pH was measured three times, and the average value was determined.

7. Particle size:

Optical microscopy was used to measure the prepared microsponges' particle size. An ocular micrometer and a stage micrometer were attached to the optical microsponges. The micrometer in the eyepiece was

calibrated. Using an optical microscope, the diameters of over 200 microsponges were measured at random.

- Calibration of eyepiece micrometer
- One division of the stage micrometer = 0.01 mm = 10 μ m

$$\mu = (SM/EM) \times 10$$

Where, μ - correction factor

SM- Reading of stage micrometer which coincides with reading of eyepiece micrometer (EM).

8. Zeta potential:

To assess the surface charge and electrostatic stability of the prepared microsponges, zeta potential was calculated. The degree of repulsion between similarly charged particles scattered across the medium is revealed by the measurement. By preventing particle aggregation and sedimentation during storage, a sufficient zeta potential value denotes strong physical stability. A zeta potential analyzer based on electrophoretic mobility was used for the analysis. The formulation's stability and suitability for additional pharmaceutical uses are indicated by the acquired zeta potential values. Improved dispersion stability and homogeneity of the microsp sponge system are suggested by higher absolute zeta potential values.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

1) Results of visual inspection of ibuprofen microsponges:

The color and nature of the F1-F2 formed microsponges were determined to be white and powdered, as indicated in Table No. 4. This indicates that the resulting microsponges pass the visual test for the standards.

Table no: 4 Results of Visual Inspection of Ibuprofen microsponges

Formulation code	Color	Nature
F1	White	Powdered
F2	White	Powdered not rigid

Fig no.3.Physical appearance of Microsponges

2) Percentage yield:

It was discovered that the ibuprofen drug's percentage yield in microsponges was 50%. For some applications, such topical or transdermal distribution, a PE of 50–70% is ideal. The yield percentage was computed using the formula that follows:

$$\% \text{ Yield} = \frac{\text{Practical yield of microsponges}}{\text{Total weight of drug and polymer}} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{1.5}{3.5} \times 100$$

Sr no.	Solution	pH	Mean
1.	Microsponges solution	6.47	6.49
2.		6.51	
3.		6.49	

Fig No.5. Determination of pH

=50%

3) Drug content:

A UV-visible spectrophotometer was used to measure the drug content of the manufactured ibuprofen-loaded microsponges. The drug content was represented as % w/w after the absorbance readings were transformed into concentration. The medication content of the formulation was 85%.

Fig no 4: Determination of drug content

1) pH:

The microsponges solution's standard range was 1–11, and its optimal pH of 6.48 was discovered.

2) Optical Microscope:

The prepared microsponges were consistently distributed and largely spherical in shape, according to optical microscopy. The particles had smooth surfaces and seemed distinct. There was no noticeable particle clumping or aggregation.

6) Results of particle size:

Zeta sizer analysis using the Microtrac Zeta sizer for microsponges. The Poly Dispersity Index (PDI) value

was 0.566, which was appropriate for particle size determination, and the average microsponge particle size in the diluted sample with water was 5946(d) nm.

Fig No.6.Result of particle size

7) zeta potential:

Zeta potential was measured at a temperature of 20.07°C, a viscosity of 1 mPa.s, and an electrophoretic mobility of 0.48 $\mu\text{m}^2/\text{Vs}$.

Microsponges are stable in preparation because their zeta potential was discovered to be 30 mV.zeta potential used to determine the particle surface charge.

- Zeta Potential Analysis -	- Zeta Sample Info -
<p>Measured Data</p> <p>Zeta Potential 30 mV</p> <p>Polarity Positive (Automatic)</p> <p>Mobility 0.48 $\mu\text{m}^2/\text{Vs}$</p> <p>Conductivity 0 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$</p> <p>Field Strength (Req/Act) 10 / 10.0 kV/m</p> <p>SOP</p> <p>Zeta Run Time 30 sec</p>	<p>Fluid</p> <p>Viscosity 1</p> <p>Temperature 20.07 C</p> <p>Dielectric Const 79</p> <p>Dispersant</p> <p>pH</p> <p>Concentration</p> <p>Particle Concentration</p>

Fig No.7.zeta potential

8) Entrapment efficiency:

For all microsponges, the loading efficiency of Ibuprofen microsphere formulations ranges from 33.17 to 82.76%, which is the maximum loading efficiency. This was discovered for the formulation F2, which contained more medication. Ibuprofen and ethyl cellulose are suggested.

CONCLUSION

Spherical nanoparticles are used in microsponges, a polymeric delivery technique. Depending on the level of flattening or after-feel required in the final formulation, these systems are composed of porous microspheres that range in size from 5 to 300 micrometers. Emollients, fragrances, essential oils, sunscreens, anti-infectives, antifungals, anti-inflammatory medications, and some antibiotics are among the many active chemicals that can be found in polymeric delivery systems, which are composed of porous microspheres. Polymeric materials are used to create these adaptable microsphere devices. By selecting the right polymer for injection, the rate of medication release can be changed. Because of this, research is currently being done on the Microsphere Delivery System (MDS), a cutting-edge and developing technology for the delivery of routine medications. A. Originally developed for topical distribution, the microsphere delivery technology—which makes use of bioerodible polymers and tissue engineering—is being employed for controlled oral administration. As with other novel drug carriers, drug release from microsphere can be controlled by varying the temperature, pH, and polymer solubility of the medium. Additionally, they may improve drug release, lessen side effects, and improve pharmaceutical stability. The microsphere method is a reliable way to administer medication because of its numerous advantages. Furthermore, MDS has a bright future in a variety of therapeutic formulations due to its advantageous qualities, which include continuous release, decreased irritancy, small size, self-sterility, and interoperability with several vehicles and components.

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